

A compact and light acoustic transducer using dielectric elastomer films for low frequency active noise cancellation

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Abstract

An acoustic transducer incorporating dielectric elastomer (DE) films, is proposed for active noise cancellation (ANC) setups inside the passenger compartment of ground and air vehicles, where compactness and lightness of the transducer along the effective generation of low frequency sound, are of primary concern. This transducer consists of two circular DE films in a push-pull configuration, fixed on a plastic frame. Application of electric field on a DE film, induces a change in thickness and surface area of the film, hence this configuration oscillates, generating sound. Meanwhile, the second film acts as a spring. In order to ensure effective generation of low frequency sound, the design of the transducer is based on its resonance frequency corresponding to the lower limit of the frequency range that it is able to generate. The total stiffness of the configuration depends in part on the pre-tension of the films, providing tuning ability of the resonance frequency. Simulations via finite element (FE) models confirm the accuracy of the analytical predictions.

1 Introduction

The concept of acoustic transducers incorporating piezoelectric/dielectric elastomer membranes as actuators has been around for some years. The advancements on the field of smart materials along with the constant drive to make speakers as compact and light as possible in order to serve a number of applications, from laptop and smartphone speakers to installations in air and ground vehicles, are pushing for alternatives to the traditional magnetic speakers. The concept of an extremely light push-pull acoustic transducer using DE elastomer films introduced in [1], is further examined in this paper. The trigger to revisit this concept, was to build an ANC configuration inside an aircraft cabin, where compactness and lightness of the components are of primary importance. The sound content inside an aircraft cabin mainly consists of low frequency noise coming from the rotation of the engines. Thus, the objective is to incorporate in the setup, a number of speakers with the aforementioned attributes in order to cancel this low frequency interference. Obviously, attributes such as the fidelity of the generated sound are secondary in this case. The theory and application of the ANC configuration as a whole, is beyond the scope of this paper, therefore the following analysis concerns specifically the study and parametrization of the required speakers/acoustic transducers. Specifically, the approach taken here stems mainly from the standpoint of structural dynamics while also focusing on the hyperelastic properties of the DE material and the ways of predicting and simulating its mechanical behaviour.

2 EAP Loudspeaker

2.1 Basic Principles of DE Films

A DE film acts as a capacitor and its electrical energy [2] is expressed as:

$$U_e = \frac{1}{2}CV^2 \quad (1)$$

where the capacitance is

$$C = \frac{\epsilon_0\epsilon_r A}{z} \quad (2)$$

and

- ϵ_0 : dielectric constant of free space,
- ϵ_r : dielectric constant (relative permittivity) of elastomer,
- A: elastomer area,
- z: thickness of elastomer.

The infinitesimal mechanical work on the film come as

$$dW = -Ap dz \quad (3)$$

thus the Maxwell stress induced from the electrical field is

$$p = \epsilon_0\epsilon_r \left(\frac{V}{z}\right)^2 \quad (4)$$

where the voltage to the membrane is of the form:

$$V = b + a(\sin \omega t) , a, b : const \quad (5)$$

2.2 Design

Figure 1 demonstrates the transducer incorporating two DE films attached to the plexiglass frame and tie in the middle via the polystyrene joint. The top DE film is smeared with carbon conductive grease and is driven by voltage V, while the bottom one only acts as a spring.

Figure 1: Loudspeaker incorporating dielectric elastomer films.

The notation of Fig.1:

- R_j : radius of the joint,
- R : internal radius of the frame,
- $r = R - R_j$: radius of the undeformed elastomer film minus the joint radius,
- Δr : stretch of the dielectric elastomer film in the radial direction of the diaphragm,
- θ : angle of the deformed elastomer film in the equilibrium position relative to the horizontal plane of symmetry.

2.3 Analytical Model

In order to establish a preliminary set of dimensions for the transducer, corresponding to a specific resonance frequency, a theoretical-analytical model is formulated [1, 3], to describe the relationship between the angle θ of a DE film -which essentially corresponds to certain pre-stress conditions- and the equivalent stiffness of the DE film in the direction of oscillation, as noted in Fig.1.

Figure 2: Elastomer film deformation model.

The notation of Fig.2, which shows the geometric parameters involved in the analytical deformation model of a DE film, is as follows:

- $\Delta\phi$: central angle of the infinitesimal strip measured at the centre of the diaphragm,
- t : thickness of the DE film,
- l : length in the radial direction of the diaphragm,
- $F_{\Delta\phi}$: tension between the joint and the frame,
- $A(l) = (R_j + l)(\Delta\phi)t$: cross area at length l .

The stretch of the dielectric elastomer film in the radial direction of the diaphragm is

$$\Delta r = r(1/\cos\theta - 1) \quad (6)$$

The expansion per unit length $(\Delta r)'$ is

$$(\Delta r)' = \frac{F_{\Delta\phi}}{EA(l)} \Delta l \quad (7)$$

Therefore

$$\Delta r = \int_0^r (\Delta r)' = \int_0^r \frac{F_{\Delta\phi}}{EA(l)} dl = \frac{F_{\Delta\phi}}{E(\Delta\phi)t} \log_{10} \left(\frac{R_j + r}{R_j} \right) \quad (8)$$

which leads to

$$F_{\Delta\phi} = \frac{E(\Delta\phi)t\Delta r}{\log_{10} \left(\frac{R_j + r}{R_j} \right)} \quad (9)$$

Figure 3: Mechanical equivalent model of the transducer.

The total tension \bar{F} in the direction of the principal axis of the transducer, which is essentially the $\sin \theta$ component of the summation of $F_{\Delta\phi}$ for a circle, comes as

$$\bar{F} = \int_0^{2\pi} F_{\Delta\phi} \sin \theta d\phi = \frac{2\pi Et}{\log_{10} \left(\frac{R_j+r}{R_j} \right)} r (\tan \theta - \sin \theta) \quad (10)$$

Considering that the vertical displacement of the joint comes as

$$Y_0 = r \tan \theta \quad (11)$$

the expression of the vertical force \bar{F} becomes:

$$\bar{F} = \frac{2\pi Et}{\log_{10} \left(\frac{R_j+r}{R_j} \right)} (1 - \cos \theta) Y_0 \quad (12)$$

This vertical displacement Y_0 , in the end is half of the total height of the full configuration. Therefore, the equivalent "vertical" stiffness of this DE film comes as:

$$k_{eq} = \frac{d\bar{F}}{dY_0} = \frac{2\pi Et}{\log_{10} \left(\frac{R_j+r}{R_j} \right)} (1 - \cos \theta) \quad (13)$$

In order to formulate the final expression of the resonance frequency, the mechanical equivalent model of the transducer as in Fig.3 is considered.

The dynamic equation of motion of the equivalent mechanical model of Fig.3 is:

$$m\ddot{y} + k_{eq}y - k_{eq}(-y) = m\ddot{y} + 2k_{eq}y = F(t) \quad (14)$$

Meaning that the total stiffness of the push-pull configuration is essentially two springs in parallel, namely:

$$k_{tot} = k_{eq} + k_{eq} \Rightarrow k_{tot} = 2k_{eq} = k \quad (15)$$

therefore it is twice as large as the equivalent stiffness due to the symmetrical structure of the transducer, namely:

$$k = \frac{4\pi Et}{\log_{10} \left(\frac{R_j+r}{R_j} \right)} (1 - \cos \theta) \quad (16)$$

Finally, the resonance frequency which signifies the lower limit of the reproduction frequency range of the transducer, is:

$$f_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m_j + \frac{2}{3}m_f + 2M_s}} \quad (17)$$

where

- m_j : mass of the joint,
- m_f : mass of DE film,
- $M_s(f_0) \approx \frac{8}{3}\rho R_j^3$: additional mass derived from the reactance component of radiation impedance for one side of the diaphragm, where ρ is air density.

Therefore the final expression of the resonance frequency:

$$f_0 = \sqrt{\frac{Et_f(1 - \cos \theta)}{\pi \log_{10} \left(\frac{R_j+r}{R_j} \right) \left(m_j + \frac{2}{3}m_f + 2M_s \right)}} \quad (18)$$

The term $2 \times m_f/3$ is added to take into account the effective mass of the oscillating DE films acting as springs. At last, using this analytic deformation model, allows the preliminary dimensioning of the transducer for a specific target resonance frequency.

2.4 Hyper-elastic Models

Hyper-elastic materials like silicon rubber, have the ability to experience large deformations under small loads and to retain their initial configuration, without considerable permanent deformation after removal of the load [4]. An example of such a material, specifically uniaxial stress data of a certain silicon rubber [7], is presented in Fig.4.a. Here is demonstrated a typical phenomenon in hyperelastic materials called "hysteresis" [8], where the unloading path of the stress-strain curve is different from the loading path due to reaching ultimate elongations. Figure 4.b shows the corresponding Young's Modulus $E = d\sigma/d\epsilon$ as a function of the material's strain during stretching up to 80%.

Figure 4: (a) Silicon rubber uniaxial test data. (b) Resulting Young's Modulus for $\epsilon = 0$ to 0.8.

These materials demonstrate highly non-linear stress-strain behaviour [5], consequently a simple constant modulus of elasticity is not sufficient for its description. Therefore the aim of hyper-elastic models is to characterize hyper-elastic materials and to determine a suitable Strain Energy Function (SEF).

2.4.1 Strain Energy Function (SEF)

Generally, SEF is based on the three strain invariants I_1, I_2, I_3 and expresses the energy stored in material per unit of reference volume (initial configuration) as a function of strain at the certain point in the material [4, 6]. If $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3$ are the principal stretch ratios, then:

$$I_1 = \lambda_1^2 + \lambda_2^2 + \lambda_3^2 \quad (19)$$

$$I_2 = \lambda_1\lambda_2 + \lambda_2\lambda_3 + \lambda_3\lambda_1 \quad (20)$$

$$I_3 = \lambda_1^2\lambda_2^2\lambda_3^2 \quad (21)$$

In general, hyper-elastic materials are considered incompressible, thus, $I_3 = 1$. The suitable SEF depends on the specific application seeking to characterize.

2.4.2 Yeoh Model

The Yeoh model belongs in the category of the phenomenological models which are the most commonly used. The models in this category, are approaching hyper-elasticity from the viewpoint of continuum mechanics. They are stress-strain behaviour characterized without reference to the microscopic structure. Other models of this category are the Mooney-Rivlin, Neo-Hookean, Ogden etc. The Yeoh model has an advantage over other available models, exhibiting good matching with experimental data over large strain values for given rubber compositions. Essentially, the Yeoh model is a 3^{rd} order polynomial model, based only the first strain invariant I_1 . The SEF of the Yeoh Model is defined as:

$$W = \sum_{i=1}^3 C_{i0}(\bar{I}_1 - 3)^i + \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{1}{D_i}(J_{el} - 1)^{2i} \quad (22)$$

where

- C_{i0} : material constants controlling the shear behaviour. Can be determined from uni-axial, bi-axial and planar stress tests.
- D_i : material constants controlling bulk compressibility. Estimated from volumetric tests. For fully or nearly incompressible ($\nu \approx 0.5$) rubber materials are equal to 0.
- J_{el} : elastic volume ratio.

Therefore the coefficients $C_{10}, C_{20}, C_{30}, D_1, D_2, D_3$ are needed for the application of the Yeoh hyperelastic model, which may be introduced directly if known or be calculated via interpolation of given material stress-strain data. An example of such data is presented in Fig.4. Specifically, a set of uniaxial true stress- true strain data ($\sigma_{true}, \epsilon_{true}$) of a certain silicon rubber hyperelastic material (), is used. The curve in Figure 4.b is a 2nd order polynomial interpolation of the corresponding Young's Modulus $E = d\sigma/d\epsilon$ as a function of the material's strain. Figure 5.a demonstrates the fitting of various hyperelastic models, using the appropriate ABAQUS® module, to the given set of nominal stress-strain uniaxial data for a silicon rubber hyperelastic material. Furthermore, in Figs.5.b and 5.c, the corresponding biaxial and planar curves are constructed via the calculated coefficients of each model. Observation of all three curves leads to the conclusion that indeed, the Yeoh model provides the most realistic fitting in this case.

Figure 5: Nominal Stress-Strain curves. Fitting of hyperelastic models. (a) Uniaxial data (b) Biaxial data (c) Planar Data (Test Data: red \times , Ogden: green \circ , 2_{nd} order polynomial: blue \square , Yeoh: yellow \diamond)

For the fitting of the Yeoh model to these data, the nominal (engineering) stress and strain ($\sigma_{nom}, \epsilon_{nom}$) values were calculated as:

$$\epsilon_{nom} = e^{\epsilon_{true}} - 1 \quad (23)$$

$$\sigma_{nom} = \frac{\sigma_{true}}{e^{\epsilon_{true}}} \quad (24)$$

The resulting coefficients are presented in Table 1.

C_{10} [MPa]	C_{20} [MPa]	C_{30} [MPa]	D_1	D_2	D_3
0.481	-0.105	1.814×10^{-2}	4.189×10^{-2}	0	0

Table 1: Coefficients for the SEF of the hyperelastic Yeoh model.

2.5 Transducer Dimensioning

Considering the material of the DE films as the same silicon rubber demonstrated in Fig. 4, the equation of the 2_{nd} order interpolation in Fig. 4.b describing the Young's Modulus as a function of strain, is:

$$E(\epsilon) = 26.049\epsilon^2 - 17.893\epsilon + 4.963 \quad (25)$$

In order to approximate as best as possible the non-linear behaviour of the hyperelastic material for the purpose of the parametric examination of the resonant frequency, taking the strain as $\epsilon = \Delta r/r$, it can be expressed as a function of the angle θ :

$$\epsilon(\theta) = 1/\cos\theta - 1 \quad (26)$$

Consequently, Young's Modulus may also be calculated for each angle θ . Table 2 summarizes the material properties of the DE film and joint along with other basic parameters.

t_f [μm]	ν	ϵ_r	ϵ_0 [$\frac{F}{m}$]	ρ [$\frac{kg}{m^3}$]	ρ_f [$\frac{kg}{m^3}$]	ρ_j [$\frac{kg}{m^3}$]
100	0.49	2.8	8.854×10^{-12}	1.225	1247	29

Table 2: Basic parameters and material properties

The geometric parameters of the loudspeaker have to be decided in order to achieve the target resonance frequency of $f_0 \approx 100$ Hz. A starting set of geometric parameters is selected and summarized on Table 3.

Figure 7: Resonant frequency of the transducer as a function of angle θ and thickness t_j of the joint.

R [mm]	R_j [mm]	r [mm]
40	10	30

Table 3: Geometrical parameters

Figure 6: Design of EAP loudspeaker - Initial State.

Therefore, the stiffness of the structure in the vertical direction, in the sense of the direction the films oscillate, and the mass of the joint which are the determining factors of the resonance frequency are now dependent only on the angle θ and the thickness of the joint t_j . The angle θ is essentially a direct marker of the pre-stress conditions on the DE films at the operating position of the loudspeaker and the thickness of the joint acts as a tuner of the mass. Considering the above joint and frame inner diameters constant, it is possible to examine the dependence of the resonance frequency from these parameters, which is demonstrated in Fig.7.

For practical reasons, a choice of $t_j \approx 10$ mm is indicated with the dotted light blue line along with the red dotted line for the target frequency, resulting to an angle of $\theta \approx 12^\circ$.

3 FEM Models

For verification of the results from the analytic deformation model, a FEM based model is simulated. The goal is to confirm that the dimensioning of the loudspeaker based on the theoretical calculations, indeed leads to the target resonance frequency.

3.1 Stiffness Comparison

In order to check the validity of the analytical deformation model, a vertical static load is applied on the perimeter of the top frame, leading to the state shown in Fig.8.b, making it possible to calculate the stiffness

Figure 8: (a) Undeformed EAP loudspeaker. (b) EAP loudspeaker under vertical static load.

Figure 9: (a) Mechanical equivalent model of the static loading of the top frame. (b) Resulting stiffness as function of vertical displacement of the top frame. Comparison between FEM and analytical results.

of the configuration allowing direct comparison with the corresponding results acquired from the analytic deformation model.

It should be noted that in this stage, the DE films act as two springs in series because of the nature of the static loading. Meaning that the mechanical equivalent of this loading case has the form of Fig.9. Therefore the FEM results of the expression $d\bar{F}/dY_0$ are compared with the theoretical $k = k_{eq}/2$. The comparison between the analytic and FEM results is demonstrated in Fig.9.b. It is observed that the analytic and FEM models are almost in perfect agreement. Thus, it is expected that stiffness will not be a factor for any possible deviations from the resonance frequency estimated by the FEM model.

3.2 Modal Analysis

Using the full configuration FEM model, by importing pre-stress conditions on the transducer, namely vertical displacement of the top frame corresponding to the theoretically estimated angle $\theta = 12^\circ$ of the DE films, the frequencies of the modes are calculated via modal analysis. The results are presented in the Table 4 for the first six modes.

Mode	1	2	3	4	5	6
Frequency [Hz]	95.79	117.57	117.70	133.07	133.70	134.16

Table 4: Eigenfrequencies

Therefore the frequency of the first mode from Table 4 shown in Fig.10, corresponds to the resonance frequency of the transducer $f_0 = 95.79 [Hz]$, which compared to the theoretically estimated $f_0 = 101.27 [Hz]$,

presents a deviation of 5.42%. The conclusion from these results, is that the slight deviation of the estimated resonance frequency between the FEM and analytical models comes down to the exact estimation of the effective mass of the transducer, especially considering Fig.9.b showing that the stiffness comparison is excellent. In general, the analytical deformation model, appears as a perfectly adept method to estimate the resonance frequency and thus act as the basis for the dimensioning of the transducer.

Figure 10: Graphical representation of the first 6 modes of the transducer (Deformation scale factor=1). (a) 1st, (b) 2nd, (c) 3rd, (d) 4th, (e) 5th, (f) 6th

4 Conclusions

The investigation of this concept for an acoustic transducer, mainly from the perspective of structural dynamics, demonstrated certain facts. Firstly, the theoretical model for the calculation of the resonant frequency and dimensioning of the transducer, was verified by the FEM simulations while also incorporating the hyperelastic properties of the material in the analysis. Also, it is clear that the construction of a compact and light transducer tuned for low frequency sound generation is possible through simple procedures and a cheap configuration overall. However, the exclusively acoustic aspects and performance of this speaker have to be examined in future research and experimental tests. Elements such as possible enclosures for the transducer and the required voltage levels to drive the DE films to achieve satisfactory sound levels or durability tests, are equally important and need to be investigated. Summarizing, this concept shows promise, especially considering how its main features line up to potential applications, market and technology trends.

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References

- [1] T. Sugimoto, A. Ando, K. Ono, Y. Morita, K. Hosoda, D. Ishii, K. Nakamura, *A lightweight push-pull acoustic transducer composed of a pair of dielectric elastomer films*. The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America, 134(5) (2013) , EL432-EL437.
- [2] F. Carpi, D. De Rossi, R. Kornbluh, R. E. Pelrine, P. (Eds.) Sommer-Larsen, *Dielectric elastomers as electromechanical transducers: Fundamentals, materials, devices, models and applications of an emerging electroactive polymer technology*, Elsevier, (2011).
- [3] J. Zhu, S. Cai, Z. Suo, *Resonant behavior of a membrane of a dielectric elastomer*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 47(24) (2010), 3254-3262.
- [4] M. Shahzad, A. Kamran, M. Z. Siddiqui, M. Farhan, *Mechanical characterization and FE modelling of a hyperelastic material*, Materials Research, 18(5) (2015), 918-924.
- [5] L.A. Wood, *Uniaxial Extension and Compression in Stress-Strain Relations of Rubber*, J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand (1977), 57-63.
- [6] D.S. Simulia, *Abaqus 6.11 theory manual*. Providence, RI, USA: DS SIMULIA Corp (2011).
- [7] J. Bergstrom, (2004, January 25). *Experimental Data Files for Various Polymers*. Retrieved from <https://polymerfem.com/articles/experimental-testing/25139-experimental-data-files-for-various-polymers>.
- [8] M. Wadham-Gagnon, *Hyperelastic Modelling of Rubber Behaviour in Finite Element Software*, Doctoral dissertation, McGill University Libraries (2006).

